

Multiple myeloma as cerebral venous sinus thrombosis: An unusual case report

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14 Apr. 2020
Accepted: 23 May 2020
Published: 30 June 2020

Abstract

Introduction

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis is a common condition associated usually with hypercoagulable states such as puerperium and inherited as well as acquired coagulopathies.

Case presentation

A 67-year old male presented with acute onset, moderately severe headache of 2 weeks duration without vomiting, fever, neck pain or stiffness. He was admitted in a confused state following two episodes of left focal seizures with secondary generalization.

Conclusion

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis is an unusual presenting manifestation of multiple myeloma and the latter should be considered in the differential diagnosis of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis.

KEYWORDS

Anticoagulant, bone, monoclonal, myeloma, patient, thrombosis

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INTRODUCTION

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis is considered as a common condition associated with puerperium and acquired coagulopathies. Multiple myeloma is a type of hematological malignancy with a higher frequency rate. In this pathophysiological condition malignant plasma cell infiltration of the bone marrow occurs with a prominent appearance of high levels of monoclonal protein in serological sample and urine. Multiple myeloma targets older age group individuals. We report a case of a 67-year-old man who was presented with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis and later identified to suffer with advanced stage of multiple myeloma.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 67-year old male was admitted to our neurology Department after two episodes of seizure and loss of consciousness. Later he reported of severe headache for past 3 weeks duration which was acute onset. There was no other sign and symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, fever, neck pain or stiffness. There was no co-morbid condition associated with him. Biochemical investigations revealed anaemia (Hb=7 g/dl), with microcytic, hypochromic type. ESR measured 60 mm in the first hour. His total proteins of 9 g/dl. white cell blood count 3,700/ μ L, and platelets 233,000/ μ L. Liver function tests, C-reactive protein, and ammonia was unremarkable. Renal parameters, serum calcium, phosphate, blood glucose, coagulation parameters were in normal range. Bone marrow aspiration revealed 45% of plasma cells. X-ray revealed prominent osteoporotic bone lesions (Figure 1)

Figure-1 X-ray image of osteoporotic bone lesions

Non-contrast Head CT showed hemorrhagic infarct of the both side temporo-parietal area, without any prominence of bone destruction. MRI showed hemorrhagic infarcts in the temporo-parietal area. injection of contrast showed left sigmoid sinus and left proximal jugular vein thrombosis.

The patient was started on anticoagulant therapy. He has also received antiedema measures in the form of IV mannitol 0.25 g/Kg every six hours for five days and anticoagulation with low molecular weight heparin followed by oral warfarin maintaining INR between 2-2.5. His clinical course slowly improved.

Figure 2: CT contrast showing venous sinus thrombosis, involving the superior sagittal sinus, straight sinus and transverse sinus (red arrows).

For a period of next two years he was treated with melphalan 5 mg/day and prednisolone 1 mg/kg/day. Bone marrow aspiration at the end of two and half years showed 4% plasma cells. We assessed for Protein C and S and anti-thrombin III deficiency, factor V Leiden mutation, anticardiolipin antibodies and lupus anticoagulant which was negative 4 months after stopping anticoagulation.

DISCUSSION

Multiple myeloma is a type of B-cell malignancy characterized by a monoclonal expansion and accumulation of abnormal plasma cells in the bone marrow compartment. Neurological manifestations in myeloma is heterogenous including peripheral neuropathies, spinal radiculopathies, cranial nerve palsies, spinal cord compression, and a host of metabolic encephalopathies. [1]

Thrombosis and thromboembolism may occur in myeloma, during the course of treatment. Thalidomide-related side effects include peripheral neuropathy and deep venous thrombosis (DVT). Peripheral neuropathy limits the dose and duration of treatment. Central retinal vein occlusion, pulmonary thromboembolism, Budd-Chiari syndrome, and localized skin gangrene, attributed to patient immobility, low grade disseminated intravascular coagulation, antiphospholipid antibodies or hyperviscosity also common. [2-8]

Most of cases pathogenesis of thrombotic complications

remains a mystery. immunoglobulins on fibrin structure, procoagulant autoantibody production, effects of inflammatory cytokines are prominent underlying causation. von Willebrand factor antigen, and procoagulant factor VIII, protein S deficiency, lupus anticoagulant activity is well documented. [9-11]

The predisposing cause for hypercoagulable tendency in this patient is unknown. We did not find any evidence of thrombocytosis known to occur as overcompensation in response to low grade disseminated intravascular coagulation and thrombocytolysis. Robert et al analyzed 42 patients with lymphoplasmacytic disorders to confirm the association of monoclonal gammopathies with hemostatic defects and he found high incidence of abnormal coagulation tests in myeloma patients. [12]

The renal and serum electrophoreses were in the normal range in our patient. A vast majority of the patients serum electrophoresis identifies M-protein with minimal monoclonal light chains. The remaining 10-20% usually show only free monoclonal light chains or IgD paraprotein present at very low level or have non-secretory myeloma. [13] Although CSF study was not done in our patient, leptomeningeal myelomatosis as cause of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis in myeloma can be ruled out easily as a part of our treatment. So we feel that even though we could not demonstrate hypercoagulability in our patient at outset, hypercoagulability secondary to paraproteins resulted in cerebral venous sinus thrombosis to him.

CONCLUSION

We conclude that cerebral venous sinus thrombosis can be associated with multiple myeloma and it should be taken into consideration for differential diagnosis of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis if necessary.

ABBREVIATIONS

deep venous thrombosis (DVT)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the patient for participating in this study.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

- a. Study planning: AP, JH
- b. Case report: AP
- c. Follow up: AP, JH
- d. Interpretation: AP
- e. Manuscript writing: AP, JH
- f. Manuscript revision: AP, JH
- g. Final approval: AP, JH
- h. Agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work: AP, JH

FUNDING

No funding was available for this research

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

All data and materials are included in the manuscript, no separate data is available.

ETHICS APPROVAL AND CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE

Ethical approval was taken, and consent was taken from the participant.

CONSENT FOR PUBLICATION

Consent was taken from the patient for publication.

COMPETING INTERESTS

None declared.

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